

Teaching Strategies and Learning Competencies of Learners in Daliaon District, Toril Davao City Division

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the teaching strategies employed by teachers and the learning competence of learners in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City. There were 100 of our 134 teachers considered respondents in the study, as determined by the Raosoft calculator. The findings revealed the extent of teachers' teaching strategies and learners' learning competence in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City. The study's findings revealed the extent to which teachers employed various teaching strategies in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao, including the inquiry method, Practical work approach, Problem-solving solution, and Use of Information and Communication Technology, with an overall mean of "extensive." On the other hand, the extent of learners' learning competence in Daliaon District, in terms of mastery of knowledge, learning outcomes, and learners' engagement, is extensive. There is a notable correlation between the teachers' teaching strategies employed by educators and the learning competence of students in the Daliaon district of Davao City in the domain of the educator's problem-solving solution and use of information communication and technology considerably impact the learners' ability to acquire knowledge, as evidenced by the significance of their corresponding p-values below 0.05. Addressing challenges and utilizing information and communication effectively. The two domain indicators, the inquiry method and the practical work approach, are insignificant.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher's teaching strategy
2. learning competence of learners
3. Daliaon District Toril, Davao City

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1. Introduction

In the classroom, effective instructional strategies are essential for engaging students and fostering meaningful learning experiences. Without a structured approach, teaching can become disorganized and fail to connect with learners. Utilizing diverse techniques, such as discussions, group projects, and hands-on activities, promotes active participation, supports differentiation to meet varied needs, and develops critical thinking through inquiry-based methods. Ongoing feedback and reflection help students set goals and monitor their progress, while positive teacher-student relationships create a supportive environment that enhances collaboration. Incorporating real-world applications makes learning relevant and encourages the transfer of skills across contexts, ultimately preparing students to thrive in a dynamic and complex world. Longstanding concerns have persisted globally regarding issues in primary-level math-

ematics education. In 1935, UNESCO started to examine the various stages of mathematics instruction. Subsequently, other prominent assessment systems, such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), have been used to evaluate the effectiveness of educational practices across different countries. Research from TIMSS has demonstrated a clear link between the limitations imposed by students' lack of preparedness and their overall achievement levels (Mullis, Martin, Foy, Kelly, Fishbein, 2020).

The World Bank reports that 80 percent of children in low-income countries are unable to read and comprehend a simple text by the age of 10. The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened existing educational challenges. Around 94% of children worldwide have faced school closures, leading to significant learning setbacks that are further amplified by pre-existing inequalities, especially among marginalized student populations. Many nations and educational institutions temporarily shifted to online learning during closures. However, this solution is not feasible everywhere, as less than half of households in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) have internet access (Radhika Bhula John Floretta, 2020). The pandemic also forced educators to adapt their methods to engage learners differently. Teachers developed new strategies for teaching, communication, and assessment to maintain quality instruction (Hodges, Moore, S., Lockee, Trust, Bond, A., 2020). As a result, the shift from traditional face-to-face teaching to technology-based approaches became apparent, highlighting the limitations of in-person interaction. In traditional settings, teachers benefit from non-verbal cues like body language, facial expressions, and voice modulation to enhance understanding. During the pandemic, these elements could not be utilized directly, prompting teachers to slow down their explanations to ensure students could follow

and grasp key concepts in online lessons (Hasan Bao, 2020). From a broader national perspective, it is crucial to establish new standard approaches to help policymakers and educators identify both opportunities and challenges in the teaching and learning processes during COVID-19. Curriculum redesign for the new normal is urgent, providing guidance on goals, content, teaching methods, assessment, and strategies to address emerging problems effectively (Cahapay, 2020). Mathematics, in particular, remains a difficult subject for many learners. Despite widespread awareness of the issues surrounding math education, little proactive effort has been made to address them. Preconceived notions about mathematics—some innate and others influenced externally—often discourage students from pursuing the subject. While some learners possess innate talent, many do not, leaving external agents responsible for nurturing and developing mathematical skills. It is essential to inspire, guide, and cultivate these talents to make practical application of mathematics a natural part of everyday life (Iwuananwu, 2021). The shift from teaching mathematics in English to using the learners' mother tongue in primary education has brought significant challenges for teachers. The Philippines adopted a multilingual policy in 2012-2013, reinforced by Republic Act No. 10533, which established principles for multilingual education. This approach uses the students' first language as the medium of instruction for all subjects from pre-kindergarten through grade three, with Filipino and English taught separately. Teaching mathematics in the mother tongue is believed to facilitate better understanding of concepts, as students are more comfortable with their first language (Tortola, Riches L., 2023). Since the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy, various studies have highlighted difficulties in its execution. Challenges include translating mathematical terminology accurately, providing appropriate exer-

cises and activities, and addressing the lack of textbooks in the native language, limited vocabulary, and insufficient teacher training—issues reported in schools in Dumaguete and other regions (Tundag et al., 2020). In the Philippine context, many students consider English their primary language for mathematics, even at home, which causes confusion and diminishes interest. Transfer students with different native languages struggle to comprehend lessons and participate actively, further complicating the learning process (Baquiller Abellon Jr., 2021). In light of the preceding discussion and recognizing the scarcity of localized research, the investigator seeks to explore the ways in which pedagogical strategies enhance students' learning capabilities, the obstacles faced by educators in delivering core subjects, and the significance of these strategies in bolstering academic achievement in the core subjects within the Davao District, Division of Davao City. The researcher serves as an educator in a public elementary institution in the Davao District within the Division of Davao City. She believes that the educator's foremost duty is to evaluate the student's comprehension and remove the obstacles to learning that would foster a favorable educational experience. Consequently, the researcher felt compelled to undertake this study to identify additional factors that enhance the quality of teaching in public schools. This research posits that the strategies teachers employ in their instruction play a crucial role in shaping the learning competence of elementary students. Consequently, the investigator sought to examine the aforementioned variable. Furthermore, the study's findings are important for advancing education, especially within the local context. Ultimately, the outcomes of this undertaking would assist us in devising suitable strategies to enhance the educational framework.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is grounded in Vygotsky's Social Development Theory, which is

one of several influential educational theories explaining how individuals acquire knowledge and develop learning competencies. Vygotsky's theory highlights the significance of social interaction and scaffolding in the learning process. Alongside this, connectivism—a more contemporary perspective—emphasizes the importance of forming connections and building knowledge networks, especially in the digital age. These theoretical foundations also underpin competency-based education, which prioritizes demonstrated mastery of specific skills over simply following a fixed curriculum. Developing learning competencies is essential for lifelong learning, and teacher preparation programs play a critical role in equipping educators with the tools needed to foster these competencies in their students. While competency-based learning focuses on skill mastery, connectivism emphasizes networks and digital resources, and Vygotsky highlights the importance of social support and structured guidance. Insights from constructivism, behaviorism, and cognitivism further enrich our understanding of how people learn. Instructional and competency frameworks also outline the interpersonal and facilitation skills educators must have to guide student growth effectively. Additionally, this research draws on Jerome Bruner's (1973) theory of scaffolding. Bruner proposed that when learners are introduced to new ideas, they benefit from active support provided by teachers and adults. Initially, students rely heavily on this guidance, but as their understanding and skills grow, the support can be gradually reduced. This process mirrors construction scaffolding, which is removed as a structure becomes self-supporting. Scaffolding in education simplifies complex choices for students, allowing them to focus on mastering specific skills or knowledge. Bruner advocated for a spiral curriculum, where students revisit and build on foundational concepts over time, progressing from simple to more complex levels of understanding. This approach aims

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

to develop independent problem-solving skills rather than simply transmitting information. According to Bruner, education should foster symbolic thinking and encourage students to discover principles independently, with teachers facilitating inquiry and discussion rather than relying on rote instruction. Effective teaching involves designing lessons that help students establish connections among ideas, utilizing the spiral curriculum model to structure discovery-based learning. Teachers should constantly create opportunities for students to explore new concepts, providing tailored support based on each student’s developmental stage. This scaffolding can be delivered not only by teachers but also through teaching assistants, parent volunteers, or more advanced peers. As students

become more competent, educators should encourage peer collaboration and recognize when learners are ready to work independently, gradually withdrawing support. The concept of “scaffolding” describes the temporary support learners receive to acquire new skills or complete tasks. Just as scaffolding surrounds a building under construction, learners may require various supports—such as prompts, guiding questions, hints, written materials, or physical tools—from teachers and parents to make progress. The conceptual paradigm of the study is shown in Figure 1. The study’s independent variables (teaching strategies) comprise the following indicators: Inquiry Method, Practical Work Approach, Problem Solving Approach, and Use of Information and Communication Technology.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the research methods that directed this investigation. It included the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedures, ethical considerations, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study utilized a non-experimental, quantitative approach, specifically adopting a correlational research design. According to Haas and Hadjar (2020),

quantitative designs are considered a benchmark for rigor in the research process. Incorporating various research perspectives can enhance the effectiveness of teaching strategies and learning competencies within the Davao City context.

A quantitative descriptive-correlational method was used to accomplish the study's objectives and to gather pertinent data, insights, and information. Research design serves as a strategic plan developed to address particular research questions (McCombes, 2019). It includes the procedures for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data, and it defines the overall approach to investigating the primary concern of the study, making it a crucial part of the research proposal. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a methodology focused on quantifying both data collection and analysis, typically following a deductive process grounded in theory testing and informed by empiricist and positivist traditions. In non-experimental research, the independent variable was not manipulated; instead, researchers observed variables as they naturally occurred. Descriptive research systematically documents and characterizes the features of a phenomenon or population. This design involves collecting data through methods such as observation or surveys, and summarizing the findings using statistical tools like means, medians, and frequencies. Often, descriptive research serves as a preliminary step that helps identify trends and relationships, which can be explored further using other research approaches (Pallant, 2020).

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The ethical considerations section of this study addresses the principles that ensure the protection and well-being of the student respondents involved. This includes maintaining confidentiality, obtaining informed consent, ensuring the voluntary nature of participation, and conducting the research with integrity and respect for the rights of all respondents.

2.3. Research Respondents—The participants in this study were elementary school teachers from Davao City, specifically from the Davao District, during the 2024–2025 academic year, all of whom had at least five years of teaching experience. The number of respondents was determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator, incorporating a 5% margin of error. Teachers were randomly selected from the seven elementary schools within the Davao District, resulting in a sample of 100 out of a total population of 134. These educators have extensive experience in elementary education, particularly in fostering critical thinking and reading motivation. A simple random sampling method was applied to select participants from each school, effectively minimizing selection bias and ensuring that the sample accurately represented the overall teacher population in the district. This approach also strengthened the validity and reliability of the study's results, consistent with established standards in educational research (Creswell Creswell, 2021). A sample size of 100 respondents was considered appropriate for the mediation model and the descriptive-correlational analyses conducted in this research. This number provided sufficient statistical power to identify significant relationships between variables, such as the impact of AI-driven learning tools on teachers' approaches to reading motivation and critical thinking (Hayes, 2022). Moreover, the chosen sample size supported practical and efficient data collection within the parameters of the study.

2.4. Research Instrument—This research employed two primary instruments to evaluate the main variables, including teaching strategies adapted from Baquiller et al. (2021) and modified to align with the present study's context. The scale provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing teacher respondents' perspectives on the role of teaching strategies in supporting elementary students' learning competence. This

tool is particularly suitable for the study, as it yields valuable insights into the ways teaching strategies contribute to learning development.

Data were gathered using a 5-point Likert scale, with responses interpreted according to the following categories:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Teaching Strategies

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teaching strategies are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teaching strategies are often evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teaching strategies are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teaching strategies are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teaching strategies are not yet evident.

The Learning Competencies of Learners, developed by Ryan, S., Cox, J. (updated 2020), was employed to learn the competence of elementary learners in Daliaon, Davao City. The study "Learning Competence of Elementary Learners" describes by three indicators, namely: student's mastery of knowledge, Learning outcomes, and Learner Engagement, wherein the purpose of the questionnaire is to evaluate re-

spondents' thought processes, their capacity to recognize assumptions, and their ability to distinguish between pertinent and irrelevant information in order to determine how they approach problem-solving and decision-making. Similar to the Learning Competencies of Learners were assessed using a 5-point Likert-type scale, with interpretations as follows:

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—Upon validating the research questionnaire, the researcher employed a systematic approach to data collection, starting with obtaining the necessary permissions to conduct the study.

these letters to the dean's offices, ensuring clear communication of the study's objectives and gaining their cooperation.

Securing Permission to Conduct the Study
The first step involves obtaining formal authorization, which begins with an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., in Davao City. This endorsement was accompanied by permission letters addressed to the School Division superintendent of Davao City. The researcher delivered

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire

After receiving approval from the college deans, the researcher distributed the research instruments to the selected participants during the 2024-2025 academic year. The researcher directly managed the distribution process, providing respondents with a brief introduction to the study's objectives and significance. This orientation was designed to help participants

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Learning Competencies of Learners

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The learning competencies of learners are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The learning competencies of learners are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learning competencies of learners are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learning competencies of learners are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learning competencies of learners are not yet manifested.

understand the context of the survey and emphasize the importance of providing sincere and thoughtful answers. The questionnaires were distributed simultaneously, allowing all respondents sufficient time to complete them in a distraction-free environment. Once the questionnaires were completed, the researcher promptly collected them to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data

Once the questionnaires had been retrieved, the researcher collated and analyzed the data statistically. The responses were systematically

aggregated, with each respondent’s scores organized according to the specific measured indicators. The data were then entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for comprehensive analysis and interpretation. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to analyze the data, allowing for a detailed examination of the relationships between parental involvement, learners’ motivation, and reading proficiency. This rigorous analytical process would ensure the findings were accurate and meaningful, providing valuable insights into the research questions.

2.6. Data Analysis—Both descriptive and parametric statistical methods were utilized for data analysis. Measures such as averages, frequencies, and means were used to summarize the teaching strategies and learning competence of elementary students. For parametric analysis, the Pearson product-moment correlation coef-

ficient and regression analysis were applied to examine the relationships between the independent and dependent variables, as well as their respective sub-variables or constructs. A significance level of 0.05 was used to assess the results. The analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software to ensure efficiency and precision.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter outlines the findings derived from the collected data, organized in accordance with the study’s initial objectives outlined in the first chapter. It covers the school feeding program, learning outcomes, and the notable correlations between them.

3.1. *The Extent Of The Teaching Strategy In Terms Of The Inquiry Method* —Summary of Extent of the Teaching Strategy of Teachers

Table 1 provides a comprehensive summary of the teaching strategies employed by teachers. The overall mean of the teaching strategy employed by educators was 3.92, indicating a comprehensive approach frequently observed among them. Furthermore, the degree of teaching strategies employed by educators is notable: the Inquiry Method (4.05) is widely utilized; the Practical Work Approach (4.01) is also prevalent; the Problem-solving Approach (3.76) is frequently applied; and the Use of Information and Communication Technology (3.85) is sim-

ilarly widespread. Teaching methods are essential to the teaching and learning process, as they have a significant impact on how engaged, understanding, and successful students are overall. Teachers who employ effective methods are better able to engage students, encourage their participation, and adapt their teaching to accommodate different learning styles. In the classroom, teaching methods are pretty important. If teachers did not have a plan, they would simply present information to students that did not interest or connect with them. Techniques engage people, encourage them to interact with one another, and make the material more engaging.

Table 1. Summary of Extent of Teaching Strategy of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Inquiry Method	4.05	Extensive
Practical Work Approach	4.01	Extensive
Problem-Solving Approach	3.76	Extensive
Use of Information and Communication Technology	3.85	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.92	Extensive

Munna and Kalam (2021) backed this idea by saying that the teaching and learning process may be seen as a way for teachers to pass on knowledge to pupils. It is called the integration of different parts of the process, where a teacher sets learning goals, makes teaching materials, and puts the teaching and learning plan into action. Conversely, learning is a fundamental aspect that a teacher must contemplate while educating kids. Their paper examined numerous academic journals, pedagogical approaches, and inclusive behaviors to evaluate teaching efficacy in the context of higher education. The research aims to evaluate the efficacy of teaching in a higher education context. The study employed experimental research

methodologies, chiefly reflective practices, utilizing literary forms to examine the theory and bolster practical applications from university experiences. The research findings indicate that offering affirmative and sufficient formative and developmental feedback, as well as incorporating role-play, significantly enhances students' confidence and self-esteem. An active learning environment also fosters diversity and helps students and teachers grow academically in school. The research findings will help educators establish and implement an inclusive teaching and learning environment to enhance learners' aspirations and academic performance. This study of Aiman Zahid and Ali Nawab (2025). Investigates the influence of educators' instruc-

tional methods on learners' approaches to studying, highlighting the frequent neglect of emphasizing "how" to study effectively over merely "what" to study. The study employed qualitative methods and included 12 student-teachers participating in a B.Ed. Program at a higher education institution in Pakistan. Data collection involved conducting semi-structured interviews and observing classroom activities. To enhance credibility and reduce bias, member checking and reflexivity were utilized. The results indicate a significant relationship between the instructional strategies educators employ and the learning approaches students adopt, showing that students are likely to utilize learning strategies that correspond with the teaching methods and assessment practices in place. The analysis delves into these strategies comprehensively, highlighting their significance for educators and teacher training institutions. This highlights the importance of considering students' learning strategies when implementing various teaching methods to foster a deeper understanding.

3.2. *Learning Competence Of Learners In Terms Of Mastery Of Knowledge* —The Summary of Learner Competence of The Learners In Daliaon District, Davao City

Table 2 summarizes the Learning Outcomes of The Learners in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City. The table shows that it yielded an overall mean score of 3.91, with a descriptive rating of 'extensive', indicating that students often exhibit this skill. Mastery of knowledge and learners' engagement received the high-

The result is consistent with the study by Bilbar (2020), which found that pupils' socio-demographic profiles have no significant relationship to their academic performance. However, the relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of the school's feeding program has a highly significant relationship with the nu-

est mean rating, with 3.94, indicating an extensive level; the last indicator is learning outcome, with 3.84, also indicating an extensive level. Learner competencies are vital for equipping students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes for successful learning, living, and working. They enable students to apply their knowledge in diverse situations and develop transferable skills. A competency-based approach focuses on mastery of specific skills and knowledge, allowing learners to progress at their own pace. Moreover, to prepare students for success, it is essential to focus on their competencies. This means providing them with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they need to address personal and professional challenges. Competency-based learning focuses on mastery, allowing students to progress at their own pace and fully comprehend the material. It also encourages lifelong learning by allowing students to set their own goals and actively participate in their education. This method promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills by applying information to real-life situations, and it also fosters collaboration and communication by enabling people to work together and enhance their interpersonal skills. Competencies also enable students to create their learning paths, which cater to the diverse needs of learners and foster student independence and intrinsic motivation. Putting learner capabilities first ultimately prepares people to excel in a world that is constantly evolving.

tritional status in initial BMI as well as with the nutritional status in recent BMI. It further concluded that there is no significant relationship between the school's feeding program and the pupils' academic performance. In the contemporary educational system, students' ability to manage and regulate their learning process independently holds a high place in the hierarchy

Table 2. Summary of Learning Outcomes of the Learners in Daliaon District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Mastery of Knowledge	3.94	Extensive
Learning Outcome	3.84	Extensive
Learners' Engagement	3.94	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.91	Extensive

of educational goals and key competencies, enabling them to cope successfully with everyday life situations and problems. Due to its central role in achieving the quality of learning and student performance in and out of school, self-regulated learning, or learning-to-learn competence, has become one of the key constructs in education (Boekaerts and Cascallar, cited in Letina, 2020). Besides understanding and learning skills, the learning-to-learn competence encompasses attitudes, values, and beliefs that enable a person to develop efficiency, flexibility, and self-organization in learning in various contextual frameworks (Smith, cited in Letina, 2020). Based on these characteristics, it can be defined as a meta-competence because it significantly impacts the acquisition and application of other competencies. The European education policy emphasizes learning competence as one of the key competencies that every European citizen should develop, in response to the accelerated global changes, which prompt educational activities to prepare students for coping with these changes and train them for lifelong learning. Learning to learn is a process that focuses on an individual's self-awareness as a student, including motivation to learn, learning goals, preferred learning strategies, and cooperation with other students. During life, especially during the intensive education process, the indi-

vidual, mostly unconsciously, develops awareness of themselves as a student and, based on that awareness, shapes their learning strategies. The learning-to-learn competence implies an awareness of the concept of learning and its essence, as well as the ability to adapt that process if some limitations occur. The learning-to-learn competence involves grasping the deeper meaning of a particular material's structure during the learning process. It can lead to a critical awareness of the assumptions, rules, and social expectations that affect humans.

3.3. Relationship Between Teaching Strategy and Learning Competence of the Learners—The results of the analysis of the relationship between the Teaching Strategy and the Learning Competence of learners in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City, are presented. A bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson product-moment correlation, was employed to determine the relationship among the mentioned variables. Table 3 presents the Teaching Strategy and Learning Competence of the Learners, with a p-value of less than 0.05 at a two-tailed significance level ($r = 0.866, p < 0.05$). This means that the extent of the school feeding programs or activities will also increase the learning outcome with which they are significantly associated.

Teaching styles are often positively correlated with learners' academic competence. Con-

sequently, effective teaching tactics correlate positively with learners' competence. A well-

Table 3. Relationship Between School Feeding Program and Learning Outcome of the Learners

Variables	Pearson r	Number of Cases	Sig. (2-tailed)
School Feeding Program and Teaching Strategy	.866**	100	<.001
School Feeding Program and Learning Competence	—	—	—

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

chosen technique can significantly enhance student engagement, promote critical thinking, and deepen comprehension of the subject matter, ultimately leading to improved academic performance and readiness for future endeavors. The study by Asmawati Malkan (2020) found that a teacher is better equipped to instruct students and effectively utilize a variety of instructional techniques. The cognitive domain of learning serves as the foundation for instructional strategies that promote active learning, requiring active participation from learners in their activities. Other names for these active learning activities include student-centered activities or student-centered teaching. The conversation, inquiry, and demonstration approaches are among the instructional strategies that encourage active learning (Asmawati Malkan, 2020). Omar, Mohammad, Shima, Raed, and Ali (2020) declared that the primary goals of education are to help students acquire, retain, and apply knowledge; to help them form habits and create attitudes; to help them build a greater knowledge base; and to help them comprehend the fundamental concepts and guidelines of the subject matter. Psychologists have developed a variety of teaching approaches and strategies tailored to the cognitive domain of learners and learning conditions, aiming to help students achieve their learning goals (Mahasneh, 2020). Santos (2022) demonstrated that the maturity of pupils and the teacher’s ability to manage the

classroom effectively are directly related. They also underlined the connection between learning outcomes and classroom atmosphere. The current research examined the relationship between classroom teaching strategies and students’ academic achievement in higher education. The connection between classroom teaching plans and student academic success in higher education is significant because it directly impacts students’ learning outcomes and success in their educational pursuits. Effective teaching strategies can enhance student engagement, promote critical thinking, and improve their understanding of the subject matter.

3.4. *The Domain Of School Feeding Programs Influences The Learning Outcome Of The Learners* —The results of the analysis of the influence of the School Feeding Program domain on the Learning Outcomes of learners in Daliaon, Toril District, Davao City, are presented. Linear regression analysis was applied to determine the influences of each domain on the endogenous variable. As shown, both of these domains significantly influence the learning competence of elementary learners, as supported by the magnitude of their respective p-values, which are all less than 0.05. Between the two determinants, Problem-Solving (b=.830, p-value <.005) and use of Information communication (b=.122, p value<.011), both of these domains are less than probability values of <.05, are the better determinants or influencers

since for every unit increase of this variable, a corresponding rise in .830 is realized in the problem solving, similarly, an increase of .122 contributed by a unit increase in use of information communication and Technology (ICT). The two domain indicators, namely the Inquiry Method and the practical work approach, are insignificant since their p-value is greater than the $<.05$ level of significance. Therefore, both of their H_0 were rejected since the two domains do not influence the student's learning competence. The initial step toward effective teaching involves recognizing and valuing individual differences among students and implementing suitable learning strategies (Putri Sari, 2021). This research explores various instructional approaches that can be employed in the classroom to accommodate diverse learning needs. As Spencer (2020) highlights, classroom management is fundamental to teaching and greatly influences student learning outcomes. An effective classroom management plan is vital for successful teaching and learning, requiring educators to identify desirable student behaviors, minimize disruptions, and promote active participation. A well-organized classroom fosters better instructional quality, optimizes class time, and

allows for fair and accurate assessment of student progress (Cordova, Maria, Santos, 2022). Moreover, how students' output is distributed plays a key role in supporting an efficient educational process (Santos, 2022). Students have access to various resources and can adopt different learning strategies. They also have the ability to direct their own learning, regulate their emotions, and manage their preferences to accomplish their educational objectives (Alarcón Díaz, Alcas Zapata, Alarcón Diaz, Natividad Arroyo, Rodríguez Fuentes, 2019). Nikou and Economides (as cited in Munir et al., 2023) suggest that homework exemplifies a micro-learning approach, reflecting the common use of micro-strategies among students. Micro-learning involves delivering education through small, focused segments within brief, targeted activities. It emphasizes condensing educational content into manageable parts, such as short explanations, formulas, or passages. Conversely, macro strategies encompass a broader set of methods, including tracking, editing, verifying, and self-assessment. These macro approaches are more comprehensive and evolve over time, making them more difficult to define succinctly.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section outlines the researcher's final insights and suggested actions. The existing literature underpins the discussions from the initial chapters, and the conclusions serve as statements regarding the problem addressed in this research.

4.1. Findings—The study explored the connection between teachers' instructional strategies and students' learning abilities in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City. It employed a non-experimental, quantitative approach using a descriptive-correlation method. Bivariate analysis was utilized to examine the relationship between the two variables. The researcher included all 100 students out of 134 enrolled in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City, as the

study's participants or sample population. To ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the survey instrument, the researcher used modified and enhanced questionnaires that were pilot-tested at a nearby school. The study's findings, based on the statistical results, show the extent of the teachers' teaching strategies in Daliaon District, Toril Davao, in terms of Inquiry method (4.05), Practical work approach (4.01), Problem-solving solution (3.76), and

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis on Teaching Strategies and Learning Outcomes

Predictors	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
(Constant)	0.432	0.334	—	1.291	.200	Accept H ₀
Inquiry Method	0.001	0.022	0.003	0.063	.950	Accept H ₀
Practical Approach	-0.014	0.062	-0.012	-0.225	.823	Accept H ₀
Problem-Solving Approach	0.830	0.063	0.780	13.110	<.001	Reject H ₀
Use of ICT	0.122	0.047	0.153	2.578	.011	Reject H ₀

Model Summary: R = .886, R² = .751, F(4,95) = 71.475, p<.05

Use of Information and Communication Technology (3.85), with an overall mean of 3.92 or extensive or oftentimes manifested. On the other hand, the extent of the learning competence of learners in Daliaon District, in terms of mastery of knowledge, learning outcomes (3.84), and learners’ engagement (3.94), is extensive and often manifests. . The relationship between teachers’ teaching strategies and learners’ learning competence was significant, with a p-value of less than 0.01, at a two-tailed significance level ($r = .866, p < 0.05$). The scope of the school feeding programs or activities will consequently enhance the learning outcomes with which they are closely linked. The increase in any unit of the teachers’ teaching strategy will correspondingly improve the learning competence of the learners. There is a notable correlation between the teaching strategies employed by educators and the learning competence of students in the Daliaon district of Davao City. The domains of the teacher’s teaching strategy significantly impact the learners’ learning competence, as evidenced by the p-values below 0.05. Specifically, Problem-Solving ($b=.830, p\text{-value} < .005$) and the use of information and

communication ($b=.122, p\text{-value} < .011$) are particularly influential. For every unit increase in Problem-Solving, there is a corresponding increase of .830, while a unit increase in the use of information communication and Technology (ICT) contributes an increase of .122. The two domain indicators, specifically the Inquiry Method and practical work approach, are deemed insignificant, as their p-value exceeds the $p < .05$ significance level. Consequently, the null hypotheses for both domains were rejected, as they do not impact the student’s learning competence.

4.2. Conclusions—Considering the results of this study and acknowledging the limitations and constraints, including the survey questionnaire and participant count, several conclusions have been drawn: The scope of the teaching strategies employed by educators in Daliaon District, Toril, Davao City. The study’s findings, based on the statistical results, show the extent of the teachers’ teaching strategies in Daliaon District, Toril Davao, in terms of Inquiry method, Practical work approach, Problem-solving solution, and Use of Information and Communication Technology, with an

overall mean of extensive. On the other hand, the extent of the learning competence of learners in Daliaon District in terms of mastery of knowledge, Learning outcome, , and Learners' engagement is extensive. There is a notable correlation between the teachers' teaching strategies employed by educators and the learning competence of students in the Daliaon district of Davao City. The areas of the educator's problem-solving solution; and use of information and communication, and technology considerably impact the learners' ability to acquire knowledge, as evidenced by the significance of their corresponding p-values below 0.05. Addressing challenges and utilizing information and communication effectively. While the two domain indicators, Inquiry Method and practical work approach, are insignificant, several theories underpinning this study include Vygotsky's Social Development Theory. Numerous educational theories elucidate how individuals acquire knowledge and skills to enhance learning competencies. One of the key theories is Vygotsky's Social Development Theory, emphasizing the significance of social interaction and the concept of learning scaffolding. Likewise, a contemporary theory known as connectivism highlights the importance of forming connections and developing knowledge networks. Moreover, theoretical frameworks underpin competency-based learning, highlighting the importance of demonstrating mastery of specific skills. Encouraging lifelong learning necessitates cultivating learning competencies, with teacher education being essential in equipping educators with the skills and knowledge needed to support their students effectively. Competency-based learning prioritizes the mastery of skills rather than adhering to a fixed curriculum. Connectivism highlights the significance of networks and digital media, while Vygotsky's Social Development Theory underscores the importance of social interaction and scaffolding in learning. Understanding learning

processes is further enhanced by insights drawn from constructivism, behaviorism, and cognitivism. The instructional and competency skills framework delineates the interpersonal and facilitation abilities essential for educators to improve their students' learning and development effectively. This study is also guided by the scaffolding theory of Jerome Bruner (1973). Bruner believed that when children learn new concepts, they need help from teachers and other adults through active support. To begin with, they are dependent on their adult support, but as they become more independent in their thinking and acquire new skills and knowledge, the support can gradually fade. This structured interaction between the child and the adult is reminiscent of the scaffolding that supports building construction. It is slowly dismantled as the work is completed. In a particular way, scaffolding represents a reduction in the many choices a child might face so that they focus only on acquiring the required skill or knowledge. He explained that the curriculum should be organized spirally so that students continually build upon what they have already learned. This involved structured information so that complex ideas could be taught at a simplified level first and then revisited at more complex levels later. Therefore, subjects would be taught at gradually increasing difficulty levels (hence the spiral analogy). Ideally, training this way should lead children to become problem solvers. The purpose of education is not to impart knowledge but instead to facilitate a child's thinking and problem-solving skills, which can then be transferred to a range of situations.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for consideration: The Department of Education may continue supporting teachers by crafting and designing seminars and workshops that promote effective teaching strategies and encourage them to participate in school-based or division-based in-service train-

ing or LAC sessions. The school Heads may urge instructors to support their initiative by using various teaching methods to help their students learn better. Teachers should also employ a range of methods to meet the needs of their pupils when they are studying the basics of major courses. As both administrators and activists, school heads are very important to the success of schools.. They may continue to motivate teachers to persist in enhancing their pedagogical skills by employing various effective teaching tactics to elevate their students' learning capabilities. Similarly, educators should employ many ways to address pupils' learning needs in the core courses. School leaders are essential in facilitating the success of educational institutions, serving as both administrators and advocates. They are accountable for overseeing and assuring the quality of instructors' performance. Teachers can help their students enhance their reasoning and computation skills by having good attitudes in class discussions. This can help students create a favorable attitude about the three main subjects: math, science, and English. The teacher should also encourage the pupils to keep participating in school activities and tell them about the good things that might come from doing these things. The incorporation of technological tools and resources into instructional methods is something that is strongly suggested. Applications for education, online platforms, and multimedia presentations are all examples of what could fall under this category. Technology can provide increased student engagement and extra opportunities. The learning materials cater to a variety of approaches. The study's findings advised that teachers participate in ongoing professional development programs to maintain current knowledge of effective teaching methods and implement evidence-based practices. Workshops, seminars, or collaborative learning communities centered on enhancing teaching abilities could be included in this category. Developing a healthy and welcoming environment. Data should be collected through, academic records, classroom observations, and interviews. Rigorous attention will be paid to the reliability and validity of the instruments employed. Modern technology should to be used in classrooms to help students. Students should always participate in the classroom teacher's learning activities to be more effective and successful students in the future. Lastly, it is advised that a comparable or comparative study be carried out to investigate other indicators concerning teachers' teaching strategies and learning abilities, and to develop alternative remediation to address the issue of students' core subjects. The results of this study have the potential to be published in a highly respected scholarly journal within the academic community.

5. References

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